

ON COMBINATORIAL IDENTITIES OF LUCAS AND FIBONACCI NUMBERS CONNECTED TO TCHEBYSHEV POLYNOMIALS

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ABSTRACT. The present paper is on derivation of many combinatorial identities of $x_n = T_n(9)$, $y_n = U_{n-1}(9)$, $L_{6n+k} = L_k x_n + 20 F_k y_n$ and $F_{6n+k} = F_k x_n + 4 L_k y_n$, $k = 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5$ and $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$, where $T_n(x)$ and $U_{n-1}(x)$ are the well known Tchebyshev polynomials of first and second kind and L_n and F_n are the well known Lucas and Fibonacci numbers.

Keywords: Lucas and Fibonacci numbers, Tchebyshev polynomials of first and second kind, Combinatorial identities.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the recent literature, many combinatorial studies on Combinatorial entities such as Catalan numbers, Lucas numbers, Fibonacci numbers, Tchebyshev polynomials, Pell and Pell-Lucas polynomials, Brahmagupta polynomials and so on are available in abundance [2, 6, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15]. Combinatorial study combined with number theory will be an ideal platform for the derivation of many combinatorial identities such as recurrence relations, generating functions, matrix power identities, cassini determinant identities, different types of summation identities and convolution identities [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 7, 8, 9, 10, 15].

The main motivation for the present paper is the beautiful connection between (L_{6n}, F_{6n}) and $(T_n(x), U_{n-1}(x))$ given below.

$$\begin{aligned} L_{6n} &= \left(\frac{1 + \sqrt{5}}{2} \right)^6 + \left(\frac{1 - \sqrt{5}}{2} \right)^6 \\ &= \left(9 + \sqrt{9^2 - 1} \right)^n + \left(9 - \sqrt{9^2 - 1} \right)^n \\ &= 2 T_n(9) \end{aligned}$$

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and

$$\begin{aligned}
 F_{6n} &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{5}} \left[\left(\frac{1 + \sqrt{5}}{2} \right)^6 + \left(\frac{1 - \sqrt{5}}{2} \right)^6 \right] \\
 &= \frac{8}{2 \sqrt{9^2 - 1}} \left[\left(9 + \sqrt{9^2 - 1} \right)^n + \left(9 - \sqrt{9^2 - 1} \right)^n \right] \\
 &= 8 U_{n-1}(9)
 \end{aligned}$$

For the sake of simplicity, one may put $x_n = T_n(9)$ and $y_n = U_{n-1}(9)$. Then they fit so well that one may derive $L_{6n+k} = L_k x_n + 20 F_k y_n$ and $F_{6n+k} = F_k x_n + 4 L_k y_n$, $k = 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5$ and $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$. The number theory of L_n and F_n enables one to derive many Combinatorial identities mentioned in the end of the above paragraph.

2. RECURRENCE RELATIONS

For the sake of smooth computation of $\{(L_{6n+k}, F_{6n+k}) : k = 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 \text{ and } n = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots\}$, a pair of sequences, namely (x_n, y_n) described by Tchebyshev polynomials is extensively applied [4, 5, 6].

Definition:

$$x_n = T_n(9), \quad y_n = U_{n-1}(9) \quad n = 0, 1, 2 \dots$$

The pair (x_n, y_n) has the following binet form :

$$\begin{aligned}
 x_n &= \frac{1}{2} [\alpha^n + \beta^n] \\
 y_n &= \frac{\alpha^n - \beta^n}{\alpha - \beta}
 \end{aligned}$$

where $\alpha = 9 + \sqrt{80}$, $\beta = 9 - \sqrt{80}$ and $n = 0, 1, 2 \dots$.

α and β satisfy the following relations : $\alpha + \beta = 18$, $\alpha - \beta = 8\sqrt{5}$, $\alpha \beta = 1$. By applying above binet form, one can show that (x_n, y_n) satisfy the following relations which are directed by Tchebyshev polynomials [4, 5, 6].

Identities 2.1

$$\begin{aligned}
 (1) \quad x_{n+1} &= 18 x_n - x_{n-1} \\
 &= 9 y_{n+1} - y_n \\
 &= 9 x_n + 80 y_n \\
 (2) \quad y_{n+1} &= 18 y_n - y_{n-1} \\
 &= \frac{9 x_{n+1} - x_n}{80} \\
 &= x_n + 9 y_n
 \end{aligned}$$

$$n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$$

Identities 2.2

$$\begin{aligned}
 (1) \quad L_{6n+k} &= \frac{F_k x_{n+1} + (-1)^k F_{6-k} x_n}{4} \\
 &= L_k y_{n+1} + (-1)^{k-1} L_{6-k} y_n \\
 &= L_k x_n + 20 F_k y_n \\
 (2) \quad F_{6n+k} &= F_k y_{n+1} + (-1)^k F_{6-k} y_n \\
 &= \frac{L_k x_{n+1} + (-1)^{k-1} L_{6-k} x_n}{20} \\
 &= F_k x_n + 4 L_k y_n
 \end{aligned}$$

$$k = 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 \text{ and } n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$$

Proof

For $k = 0$, the six identities of result (2.2), follows directly by the binet forms of x_n, y_n, x_{n+1} and y_{n+1} .

For $k = 1$, one may apply following identities [10, 13, 15].

$$\begin{aligned}
 (i) \quad &8 L_{6n+1} = L_{6n+6} - 5 L_{6n} \\
 (ii) \quad &8 L_{6n+1} = F_{6n+6} + 11 F_{6n} \\
 (iii) \quad &2 L_{6n+1} = L_{6n} + 5 F_{6n} \\
 (iv) \quad &8 F_{6n+1} = F_{6n+6} - 5 F_{6n} \\
 (v) \quad &40 F_{6n+1} = L_{6n+6} + 11 L_{6n} \\
 (vi) \quad &2 F_{6n+1} = L_{6n} + F_{6n} \\
 &n = 0, 1, 2, \dots
 \end{aligned}$$

and express interms of x_n and y_n . The identities for $k = 2, 3, 4, 5$ simply follows by the well known relations

$$L_{6n+(k-1)} + L_{6n+k} = L_{6n+(k+1)} ; F_{6n+(k-1)} + F_{6n+k} = F_{6n+(k+1)},$$

$$k = 1, 2, 3, 4 \text{ and } n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$$

3. MATRIX POWER IDENTITIES, CASSINI DETERMINANT IDENTITIES AND GENERATING FUNCTIONS

In the literature, a matrix power identity called Brahmagupta power identity ([9], [12]) is described

$$\begin{bmatrix} \xi_n & \eta_n \\ t \eta_n & \xi_n \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \xi & \eta \\ t \eta & \xi \end{bmatrix}^n$$

for

$$\xi_n = \frac{1}{2} \left[(\xi + \eta\sqrt{t})^n + (\xi - \eta\sqrt{t})^n \right]$$

$$\eta_n = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{t}} \left[(\xi + \eta\sqrt{t})^n - (\xi - \eta\sqrt{t})^n \right]$$

When $\xi = 9$, $\eta = 1$ and $t = 80$ we obtain x_n and y_n . As a consequence we have the following Matrix power identities and Cassini determinant identities described in the following results

Identities 3.1

$$(1) \quad \begin{bmatrix} x_n & y_n \\ 80 y_n & x_n \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 9 & 1 \\ 80 & 9 \end{bmatrix}^n$$

$$(2) \quad \begin{bmatrix} y_{n-1} & y_n \\ y_n & y_{n+1} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 18 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 18 \end{bmatrix}^{n-1}$$

$$(3) \quad \begin{bmatrix} x_{n-1} & x_n \\ x_n & x_{n+1} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 9 \\ 9 & 161 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 18 \end{bmatrix}^{n-1}$$

$$n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$$

Identities 3.2

$$(1) \quad x_n^2 - 80 y_n^2 = 1$$

$$(2) \quad y_{n-1} y_{n+1} - y_n^2 = -1$$

$$(3) \quad x_{n-1} x_{n+1} - x_n^2 = 80$$

$$n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$$

Identities 3.3

$$\begin{bmatrix} 4 L_{6n+k} & F_{6n+k} \\ 20 F_{6n+k} & L_{6n+k} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 4 L_k & F_k \\ 20 F_k & L_k \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 9 & 1 \\ 80 & 9 \end{bmatrix}^n$$

$k = 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5$ and $n = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots$

Next we state the generating function of x_n, y_n, L_{6n+k} and $F_{6n+k}, k = 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5$ with the help of the identities given by (2.1) and (2.2).

Identities 3.4

$$(1) \quad \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} x_n t^n = \frac{1 - 9t}{1 - 18t - t^2}$$

$$(2) \quad \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} y_n t^n = \frac{t}{1 - 18t - t^2}$$

$$(3) \quad \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} L_{6n+k} t^n = \frac{L_k + (L_{6+k} - 18 L_k) t}{1 - 18t - t^2}$$

$$(4) \quad \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} F_{6n+k} t^n = \frac{F_k + (F_{6+k} - 18 F_k) t}{1 - 18t - t^2}$$

$k = 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5.$

4. SUMMATION IDENTITIES

By suitable rearranging recurrence relations one like below the summation identities can be derived non trivially.

$$x_k = 18 x_{k-1} - x_{k-2}, \quad k = 2, 3, \dots, n$$

Adding all we get

$$16 (x_0 + x_1 + \dots + x_n) = (x_{n+1} - x_n) + 8$$

Following the same ideas, one can derive the following summation identities :

Identities 4.1

$$(1) \quad 16 \sum_{k=0}^n x_k = x_{n+1} - x_n + 8$$

$$(2) \quad 16 \sum_{k=0}^n y_k = y_{n+1} - y_n - 1$$

$n = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots$

Next by employing

$$y_{2k+2} + 19 y_{2k} = 18 (y_{2k} + y_{2k+1}), \quad k = 0, 1, 2, \dots, n$$

We obtain

$$\sum_{k=0}^n y_{2k} = \frac{1}{320} [y_{2n+2} - y_{2n} - 18], \quad n = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots$$

Similarly one can also derive an identity for $\sum_{k=0}^n x_{2k}$. Together the result is stated below.

Identities 4.2

$$(1) \quad 320 \sum_{k=0}^n x_{2k} = x_{2n+2} - x_{2n} + 160$$

$$(2) \quad 320 \sum_{k=0}^n y_{2k} = y_{2n+2} - y_{2n} - 18$$

$$n = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots$$

Since $\sum_{k=0}^n (x_{2k} + x_{2k+1}) = \sum_{k=0}^{2n+1} x_k$, the summation identities for $\sum_{k=0}^n x_{2k+1}$ and $\sum_{k=0}^n y_{2k+1}$ can be derived directly. So we just leave it for the interested reader to figure it out. More interesting ones are square sums of x_k 's and y_k 's. Using $2L_{12k} = L_{6k}^2 + 5F_{6k}^2$ and $x_k^2 - 80 y_k^2 = 1$, one can derive $x_{2k} = 2 x_k^2 - 1 = 160 y_k^2 + 1$. As a result one may directly derive the following two square sum identities :

Identities 4.3

$$(1) \quad 640 \sum_{k=0}^n x_k^2 = (x_{2n+2} - x_{2n}) + 160 (2n + 3)$$

$$(2) \quad 640 \sum_{k=0}^n y_k^2 = \frac{1}{80} [(x_{2n+2} - x_{2n}) - 160 (2n + 1)]$$

$$n = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots$$

By making use of $L_{6n+k}^2 = L_k^2 x_n^2 + 400 F_k^2 y_n^2 + 20 F_{2k} y_{2k}$ and $F_{6n+k}^2 = F_k^2 x_n^2 + 16 L_k^2 y_n^2 + 4 F_{2k} y_{2k} : k = 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5$. One can directly derive the following square sum identities :

Identities 4.4

$$(1) \quad \sum_{r=0}^n L_{6r+k}^2 = \frac{L_{2k}}{320} (x_{2n+2} - x_{2n}) + \frac{F_{2k}}{16} (y_{2n+2} - y_{2n}) + \frac{L_k^2}{4} (2n + 3) - 100 F_k^2 (2n + 1) - \frac{9}{8} F_{2k}$$

$$(2) \quad \sum_{r=0}^n F_{6r+k}^2 = \frac{L_{2k}}{1600} (x_{2n+2} - x_{2n}) + \frac{F_{2k}}{80} (y_{2n+2} - y_{2n}) + \frac{F_k^2}{4} (2n + 3) - 4L_k^2 (2n + 1) - \frac{9}{40} F_{2k}$$

$k = 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5$ and $n = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots$

5. CONVOLUTION IDENTITIES

The binet forms (2.2) will guide the following convolution identities :

Identities 5.1

$$(1) \quad \sum_{k=0}^n x_k x_{n-k} = \frac{1}{2} [(n + 1)x_n + y_{n+1}]$$

$$(2) \quad \sum_{k=0}^n y_k y_{n-k} = \frac{1}{160} [(n + 1)x_n - y_{n+1}]$$

$$(3) \quad \sum_{k=0}^n x_k y_{n-k} = \sum_{k=0}^n y_k x_{n-k} = \frac{n + 1}{2} y_n$$

$n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$

Identities 5.2

$$(1) \quad \sum_{r=0}^n L_{6r+k} L_{6(n-r)+k} = L_{2k} (n + 1)x_n + (-1)^k 2 y_{n+1} + 20(n + 1)F_{2k}y_n$$

$$(2) \quad \sum_{r=0}^n F_{6r+k} F_{6(n-r)+k} = \frac{L_{2k}}{5} (n + 1) x_n + (-1)^{k+1} \frac{2}{5} y_{n+1} + 4 (n + 1) F_{2k} y_n$$

$$(3) \quad \sum_{r=0}^n L_{6r+k} F_{6(n-r)+k} = F_{2k} (n + 1)x_n + 4L_{2k} (n + 1)y_n$$

$k = 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5$ and $n = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots$

The identities 5.1 and 5.2 can be derived directly using the results of section 2. For more details about computation and application of Convolution identities one may refer to [2].

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